

Meeting Agenda

StEM rAising EnviRonmenTal Scientists SMART

Host: Szkoła Podstawowa z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi nr 20 im. Jana Gutenberga Fundacji Szkolnej w Warszawie

Venue: Obrzeźna 12a 02-691 Warsaw, Poland

Dates: 08.09.2025 -12.09.2025

Day 1: Monday – The study trip to Gdańsk within the SMART project

- Enhancing teachers' competencies by providing direct insight into coastal ecosystems and innovative environmental practices

Day 2: Tuesday – Welcome, Digital Creativity and Urban Heritage Walk

09:00 – 09:30 – Welcome session at the host school

09:30 – 10:15 – Guided tour of the school facilities

10:15 – 11:00 – Lecture: *Fundamentals of Tinkercad and 3D Object Design*

11:00 – 12:00 – 3D Pen Workshop – *Introduction to 3D drawing and prototyping*

12:00 – 13:00 – Lunch break

13:30 – 15:00 – Visit to Łazienki Park - urban ecosystems and the impact of urbanization on the environment

15:00 – 17:00 – Walking tour along the Royal Route to Warsaw's Old Town as a historical perspective on urban sustainability and conservation efforts

17:00 – Free time to rest or explore the city independently

Day 3: Wednesday – 3D Printing & Cultural Exploration

09:00 – 10:30 – Workshop: *Three-Dimensional Printing – Tools and Techniques*

10:30 – 12:00 – Hands-on training session: *Robots in Education* – Practical applications of robotics in the classroom

12:00 – 13:00 – Lunch break

14:00 – 15:00 – Visit to the Warsaw Uprising Museum

15:30 – 16:30 – Visit to the rooftop of the Palace of Science and Culture

16:30 – Free time to rest or explore the city independently

Day 4: Thursday – Environmental Protection in Practice

10:00 – 12:00 – Visit to the Copernicus Science Centre – an interactive exhibition on climate change, sustainability, and future tech

12:00 – 13:00 – Visit to the University of Warsaw Botanical Garden - exploring biodiversity and the role of green spaces

13:00 – 15:00 – Visit to Elektrownia Powiśle as an example of a historic industrial site adapted for modern urban use; lunch break at the site

15:00 – 18:00 – Free time to rest or explore the city independently

18:00 – 21:00 – Dinner at the Zapiecek restaurant for all partners

Day 5: Friday – Future Skills & Project Wrap-Up

09:00 – 10:00 – Session: *Showcasing 3D Prints & Wrap-up*

10:00 – 11:00 – Planning next steps in the project

11:00 – 11:45 – Evaluation and reflection session

11:45 – 12:15 – Certificate ceremony

12:15 – 12:30 – Farewell and departure preparations

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